

ACADEMICIANS' PERCEPTIONS REGARDING SUPERVISOR SUPPORT, CO-WORKER SUPPORT AND LIFE SATISFACTIONⁱ

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Abstract:

This study aimed to examine the academicians' perceptions regarding supervisor support, co-worker support and life satisfaction. In the study, a survey method in a quantitative research approach was adopted. The study was carried out with the target population, which consists of 778 academicians. Consequently, a total of 317 academicians participated voluntarily. To analyze the data correlation, Kruskal Wallis H Test and Mann Whitney U Test were computed. The results of the study revealed that life satisfaction of academicians displayed no significant difference regarding gender; on the other hand, there were statistically significant differences based on professional seniority and marital status. In addition, academicians' perceived co-worker support did not differ depending on gender and marital status while it demonstrated significant differences in relation to length of service. Moreover, academicians' perceived supervisor support showed no significant difference in terms of gender, length of service and marital status. The results of the study also indicated that there were statistically significant positive relationships between life satisfaction and perceived co-worker support, supervisor support.

Keywords: academician, life satisfaction, supervisor support, co-worker support

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Introduction

Individuals who strive to orient themselves towards globalization and transformation of the world sometimes experience problems. These problems tend to create negative emotions among researchers as well. It is observed that while providing solutions in this process, individuals focus more on outcomes and negative characteristics rather than positive aspects. On the other hand, the concept of positive psychology has recently emerged in studies and concepts such as hope, happiness, optimism, forgiveness and subjective well-being have gained importance (Gable & Haidt, 2005). One of these prominent concepts is life satisfaction.

Life satisfaction is the overall cognitive assessment related to satisfaction obtained from life in general or from specific life domains such as family, friends and the life circumstances (Çivitci, 2009). In other words, life satisfaction is the conscious experiences of individual's positive emotions over the negative ones (Frish, 2005). Life satisfaction emerges as a result of comparing what individuals expect and what they have (Tümkeya, Aybek & Çelik, 2008). The happier the individuals feel about their present circumstances and their positions in life, the more life satisfaction they will have. This condition has equal impact on the individual's work, family life and other domains of his/her life (Leung & Leung, 1992).

Occupation is an integral part of human life. Perceptions related to work life inevitably affect individuals' personal lives. In this context, job satisfaction and life satisfaction are regarded as two concepts that are interrelated and complementary and helpful in making sense of one another (Dikmen, 1995). There are various studies that explain the relationship between life satisfaction and job satisfaction (Dikmen, 1995; Kale, 2015; Keser, 2005; Özdevecioğlu & Doruk, 2009; Yiğit, Dilmaç & Deniz, 2011). For instance, in their studies Özdevecioğlu and Doruk (2009) and Keser (2005) presented a positive relationship between life satisfaction and job satisfaction. In a study conducted on policemen, it was found that increased job satisfaction resulted in increases in life satisfaction (Yiğit, Dilmaç & Deniz, 2011) and another study on hotel personnel found that the support of leaders and coworkers increased life satisfaction (Kale, 2015). As can be observed, individuals' attitudes towards their work and the perceived and experienced support at the work place affect their attachment, commitment and at the same time their life satisfaction.

Employees' job and life satisfaction is one of the most investigated topics in the field of organizational commitment. Realizing fact that having full understanding of organizational commitment factors that individuals have will provide countless benefits to the organization has made this concept vital for organizations (Balay, 2000). Also, the

fact that many different responses exist for the question of what can be done so that employees form commitment to the organization and work with relish has become the starting point for new studies for both supervisors and academicians (Turunç & Çelik, 2010).

It is important for the concept of commitment that employees are valued by their organizations, that they do not feel alone in good or bad times and that they feel the presence of organizational support (Karacaoğlu & Arslan, 2013). In this sense, the concept of perceived support emerges in studies. Perceived organizational support is a perception-based concept that shows the degree of organizational support and value perceived and felt by the employee (Yoshimura, 2003). While perceived support increases attitudes and behaviors such as commitment, job satisfaction and performance, it decreases job related stress. Therefore, it can be argued that organizational support has immense contribution to employees and the organization (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). When it is examined in definitional terms, perceived organizational support expresses the degree of support for the employees by the organization and it is known that there are other types of support provided by the organization such as supervisory support and support of coworkers which are just as important as organizational support (Giray, 2013). Studies also show that perceived supervisory support has significant impact on perceived organizational support (Eisenberger, Stinglhamber, Vandenberghe, Sucharski & Rhoades, 2002).

Bhanthumnavin (2003) defines supervisory support as the positive work relations between the supervisor and the employee and states that this support is composed of three dimensions: informational, material and emotional (Bhanthumnavin, 2000). Informational supervisory support focuses on issues related to work and is defined as the rewards, punishments, feedback, knowledge and skills that will increase the productivity of the employees. Material supervisory support is explained as the finances and human resources that will help in the realization of goals by the employees while emotional supervisory support is defined as interest, affection and value provided by the supervisor. While supervisory support includes support for employees in all dimensions, it may still not be sufficient by itself. Support provided by the coworkers is one of the ways that can be used to overcome this deficiency.

Just as supervisory support, coworker support directly or indirectly influences individuals' lives. Coworker support is the support received from individuals with whom they undertake the same or similar tasks and are involved in the same level at the hierarchy (Giray, 2013) and it carries great significance. In an organizational environment where both supervisor/leader support and coworker support are felt, employees develop positive attitudes towards work and their productivity increases

(Babin & Boles, 1996). Hence, impact of supervisory and coworker support on life satisfaction is an expected result just like their impact on job performance (Kale, 2015). Considering the fact that these types of support are required in all sectors, the importance of this support in educational organizations whose input and output are human beings and which are included in social and open systems will be more pronounced and noteworthy.

Universities and university faculty members that have serious contributions in providing products for business sectors and meet their human resources play various roles as a requirement of the mission they undertake. One of these roles requires university faculty members as intellectual workers to exert efforts to make human resources more qualified. Faculty members' psychological states, their work conditions and their job and life satisfactions are significant in the realization of this role. Considered in the framework of the definition of the term "intellectual worker", it is highly important to ensure faculty members' individual motivations serve organizational goals and that their hearts (emotions) are won in the process (Alparslan, 2015).

It is stated that an ideal academic career includes various activities such as collecting data, doing and publishing research, following the developments in the related field, engaging in lesson preparation, teaching, taking part in commissions, answering the questions from students and other academic spheres, participating in conferences, reviewing articles for journals and taking advisory roles for student groups (Kerr, 1994). It is necessary for faculty members to be satisfied with their tasks to undertake these roles successfully (Serinkan & Bardakçı, 2007). Therefore, universities which expect high performances from faculty members should provide supportive work environments (Panatik et. al., 2012) and improve work conditions in financial and psycho-social aspects (İnandı, Tunç & Uslu, 2013). It is expected that this will ensure increases in faculty members' productivity and job and life satisfactions.

Studies conducted with faculty members in the literature generally focus on job satisfaction, burn out and job related stress (Ardıç & Polatçı, 2008; Arslan & Acar, 2013; Çavuş, Gök & Kurtay, 2007; İraz & Ganiyusufoglu, 2011; Küçüksüleymanoğlu, 2007; Özel, 2009; Panatik et. al., 2012; Sloane & Ward, 2001; Terzi & Sağlam, 2008; Yıldırım & Taşmektepligil, 2011; Yoleri & Bostancı, 2012). Previous studies found that coworker and supervisor support and belief in career advancement are associated with faculty members' burn out and personal achievement perceptions (Tümkaya, 2006); there are positive relationships between period of service and job satisfaction (Esen, 2001); female faculty members place more emphasis on professional development, taking responsibility, sense of achievement and recognition compared to male faculty

members (Akman, Kelecioğlu & Bilge, 2006); faculty members' job satisfaction increases with age (Baş & Ardiç, 2002); there is a linear relationship between academic career and job satisfaction (Holden & Black, 1996; Grimes & Register, 1997; Oshagbami, 1997); compared to male academicians, female academicians are more subject to psychological intimidation while single academicians are more psychologically intimidated compared to married academicians (Cayvarlı, 2013); one of the most important problems faculty members face is insufficient wages (Anderson, Johnson & Saha, 2002; Barkhuizen, Rothman, & Tytherleigh, 2004; Tuzgöl-Dost & Cenkseven, 2007); there are significant relationships between faculty members' life satisfaction and job satisfaction (Filiz, 2014); and problems generated by the academic work environment, economic problems, negative relationships with coworkers and lack of opportunities for academic work in their own universities are the problems that cause the most unrest for faculty members (Murat, 2003). In their study, Eyüpoğlu & Saner (2009) stated that job satisfaction does not increase at the same rate as academic title and Ahsan, Abdullah, Fie and Alam (2009) mentioned the negative influences of job stress on job satisfaction. Based on Serinkan and Bardakçı's (2007) study, faculty members' job satisfaction is affected by team management, the quality of the task and decision making the most whereas payment and promotions affect job satisfaction the least. In another study conducted in Turkey, faculty members are subjected to "gossip and mockery", "being ignored or feeling excluded", "lack of exchange of important information regarding the department", "disregard for their efforts", "intellectual theft" and "verbal violence" by their coworkers and superiors (Yelgeçen-Tigrel & Kokalan, 2009). This situation affects individuals' satisfaction and productivity (Topçu, Saraçlı, Dursun & Gazeloğlu, 2012).

Efficiency of higher education institutions are related to their employees to a great extent. University faculty members' positive job and life satisfactions will increase the power of this effectiveness (Küskü, 2003). As a matter of fact, it is important for faculty members to love the work environment and find their work as meaningful and an opportunity for self-development so that they can feel satisfied. This will contribute to enjoyment of life and happiness (Filiz, 2014). In their study conducted on academicians, Doğan and Eryılmaz (2012) found that satisfying the needs related to competence, autonomy and relationships which are the basic psychological beliefs related to work will ensure that individuals will experience more positive emotions and this condition will have significant influence on their life satisfactions.

Therefore, examining faculty members' relationships with their coworkers and supervisors with whom they have constant communication at the university will be instrumental in making decisions about whether those relationships have an effect on life satisfaction. Since there are not many studies in literature related to faculty

members' life satisfactions, this study focuses on the issue along with supervisor and coworker support.

1.1. Purpose of the study

In general, this study aimed to examine faculty member perceptions related to supervisor and coworker support and life satisfaction based on gender, professional seniority and marital status variables and to determine the relationships based on these perceptions. Based on this context, the sub problems provided below were investigated:

1. What are faculty member perceptions related to supervisor support, coworker support and life satisfaction?
2. Do faculty member perceptions on supervisor support, coworker support and life satisfaction significantly change according to gender, professional seniority and marital status variables?
3. Are there significant relationships between faculty members' supervisor and coworker support and life satisfaction perceptions?

2. Method

2.1. Research model

This quantitative study utilized a relational screening model to determine whether faculty member perceptions related to life satisfaction, coworker and supervisor support changed according to independent variables. Relational screening model is a research model that aims to identify the existence and degree of change between two or more variables (Karasar, 2012).

2.2. Study universe

The universe for the study was composed of faculty members employed in Abant İzzet Baysal University for the duration of 2014-2015 academic year. 12 different faculties were included in the research. The universe consisted of 778 faculty members. The sample who participated in the study was composed of 317 faculty members. 59.6% of the participants were males and 40.4% were females. 21.5% were in the age range "20-30", 37.5% in "31-40", 29.3% in "41-50", 10.4% in "51-60" and 1.3% in "61 and older". 23.7% of the participants had "1-5 years" professional seniority, 12.9% had "6-10 years" professional seniority, 22.1% had "11-15 years" professional seniority, 15.8% had "16-20 years" professional seniority and 25.6% had "21 years and higher" professional seniority. 68.8% of the 317 participants were "married", while 31.2% were "single".

2.3. Data collection tools

A question form with four sections was used in the study as the data collection tool (ANNEX-1). The first section includes questions related to demographical variables of the participants. The second section includes "The Satisfaction with Life Scale" developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen and Griffin (1985) and adapted to Turkish culture by Şimşek (2011) to measure faculty members' life satisfaction. The third and fourth sections respectively include "Coworker Support Scale" and "Supervisor Support Scale" developed by Giray (2010).

2.4. Data collection

In order to reach the whole universe, data collection tools were individually distributed and collected by the researcher ensuring confidentiality of personal information. The study was based on voluntary participation. Faculty members were visited in their rooms and the scales were given when they expressed interest in participation and the necessary explanations were provided. Since faculty members were busy during the period due to heavy work load, it was not always possible to find them in their rooms which necessitated many individual visits to the faculties by the researcher. It was not possible to establish communication with some faculty members. Also, some of the distributed data collection tools were not returned. Distributing and collection the forms were undertaken in March and April of 2015. Total number of participants that participated in the study was 317.

2.5. Data analysis

Data obtained in the study were analyzed with the help of a statistical package program. The analyses cited below were used in data analysis: frequency (f) and percentage (%) values were calculated for the analysis of demographic information. Means and standard deviation (SD) values were used to present faculty members' life satisfaction, coworker support and supervisor support perceptions. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test was utilized to determine whether the data showed normal distribution. Normalcy distributions of all three scales showed p values smaller than 0,05. It was decided to use non-parametric tests rather than parametric tests to ensure integrity in analyses since data distribution was not equal. It is known that use of non-parametric techniques is more appropriate in such conditions (Büyükoztürk, 2013; Sümbüloğlu & Sümbüloğlu, 2012; Kalaycı, 2010). Therefore, Kruskal Wallis Test, H Test, Mann Whitney U-Test and Spearman Rho Test were utilized to present the significant differences observed in the data.

3. Findings and discussion

3.1. Findings and interpretation related to the first sub problem

Table 1: Faculty member Perceptions Related to Life Satisfaction, Coworker Support and Supervisor Support

	N	$\bar{X}$	ss
Life Satisfaction	317	4.98	1.13
Coworker Support	317	3.52	.73
Supervisor Support	317	3.16	.98

Table 1 shows that faculty member perceptions were found to be at “partially agree” ($\bar{X}$ =4.98) level regarding Life Satisfaction, “agree” ($\bar{X}$ =3.52) level regarding Coworker Support and “undecided” ($\bar{X}$ =3.12) level regarding Supervisor Support.

Life satisfaction occurs as a result of individual’s holistic assessment of his/her life and life domains (Pavot & Diener, 1993). In other words, level of life satisfaction is influenced by many different domains such as work, family, social circle and leisure time. Satisfaction in a single domain does not necessarily indicate high life satisfaction. Being an academician entails intensive study, constant development and improvement with many stress factors and this fact may significantly affect academicians’ satisfaction levels. While individuals strive to achieve what they want, they are also responsible from meeting their social obligations. Academic world is defined as an institution that requires much time, shapes individuals’ desires and wishes and necessities high level of self-sacrifice. In this sense, scientific studies compete with faculty members’ other responsibilities and commitments (Coşkuner & Şener, 2013). This state may be negatively reflected on the individual’s family and general life. Findings show that faculty members “partially agree” to life satisfaction scale. The reasons cited above may be regarded as the cause of lower life satisfaction levels.

Based on the findings related to coworker support, it can be argued that faculty members support each other as coworkers in the academic work environment. Faculty members were asked to provide responses to the questions based on their coworkers in the same department. Faculty members may not communicate with everyone in their departments or may not get along well with everyone. However, the results show that faculty members receive support from their coworkers in general. This study points to the fact that faculty members have good communication with their coworkers even though the number of supporting coworkers may not be very high.

Faculty members were asked to provide assessment related to their perceptions on supervisor support by taking their immediate supervisors into account. Employees

in academic institutions are mostly responsible from individual achievements and are not responsible towards supervisors in the same manner as can be found in the private sector. They come together with supervisors mostly in the framework of bureaucratic tasks. Therefore, they may not expect support from their supervisors in other matters. However, they may want to know that supervisors will lead them in the right direction related to administrative problems and support them in matters related to work. Results show that faculty members feel “undecided” about supervisor support.

3.2. Findings and interpretation related to the second sub problem

3.2.1. Findings related to gender variable

Table 2 presents Mann Whitney U test results. The test investigated faculty members' Life Satisfaction, Coworker Support and Supervisor Support perceptions based on gender.

Table 2: Mann Whitney U test results which investigated faculty members' life satisfaction, coworker support and supervisor support perceptions based on gender

	Gender	N	SO	ST	U	P
Life Satisfaction	Female	128	160.07	20488.50	11959.50	.86
	Male	189	158.28	29914.50		
Coworker Support	Female	128	166.53	21315.50	11132.50	.22
	Male	189	153.90	29087.50		
Supervisor Support	Female	128	154.87	19823.00	11567.00	.50
	Male	189	161.80	30580.00		

According to analysis results presented in Table 2, faculty members' life satisfaction perceptions ($U= 11959.500$, $p=.864$) do not show significant differences based on gender variable. Similarly, faculty members' Coworker Support ($U= 11132.500$, $p=.228$) and Supervisor Support ($U=11567.000$, $p=.508$) perceptions do not significantly change according to gender.

Findings in many studies that found no relationship between life satisfaction and gender are parallel with the findings of this study (For instance, see Avşaroğlu, Deniz & Kahraman, 2005; Bulut, 2007; Caner, 2015; Casas et. al., 2007; Çikrikçi, 2012; Çivitçi, 2009; Fogle, Huebner & Laughlin, 2002; Fugl-Meyer, Melin & Fugl-Meyer, 2002; Gilman & Huebner, 2006; Gün & Bayraktar, 2008; Hampton & Marshall, 2000; Hintikka, 2001; Katja, Paivi, Marja-Terttu & Pekka, 2002; Mahon, Yarcheski & Yarcheski, 2005; Melin, Fugl-Meyer & Fugl-Meyer, 2003; Rask, Åstedt-Kurki & Laippala, 2002; Seligson, Huebner & Valois, 2003). As opposed to these studies, some studies that focused on different age groups found that females had higher life satisfaction compared to males

(Aydiner, 2011; Cenkseven & Akbaş, 2007; Dorahy, 1996; Frey & Stutzer, 2002; Köker, 1991; Özben, 2013; Simpson, 1996; Tuzgöl-Dost, 2007; Ünal, Karlıdağ & Yoloğlu, 2001). There are also studies that found higher life satisfaction levels in males (Bugay, 2007; Geis & Klein, 1990; Goldbeck, Schmitz, Beiser, Herschbach & Henrich, 2007). Examining these studies conducted on different study groups shows that the impact of gender on life satisfaction changes according to factors such as place of employment, organizational culture and climate.

Although no significant differences were observed in analysis results, female faculty members' life satisfaction was higher. Even though social female gender role based traditional values and attitudes, bring with them the issue of balancing work and family life, work life ensures and increases life satisfaction for females since it supports economic independence and social status (Ulusan, 2005). In their study, Başarır and Sarı (2015) reported that female academicians experience role conflicts due to multiple tasks and responsibilities in general, cannot feel freed from traditional gender roles, have to work more compared to their male counterparts and may be of secondary importance and have to stay in the background compared to male academicians, but, on the other hand, they perceive themselves as strong and productive individuals and experience pleasure from their professions. Another study found that female faculty members are more satisfied from their work conditions and career advancements compared to male faculty members and they are able to enjoy the work environment since they do not have high expectations (Alam, Talha, Sivanand & Ahsan, 2005). Therefore, females' career advancement and obtaining the position they desire have higher impact on their life satisfaction.

Although no significant differences were observed in the analyses, female faculty members have higher level perceptions regarding coworker support. Social theorists state that females are more compassionate and relationship oriented (Chodorow, 1999). This characteristic dates back to early childhood period. Social theorists also mention indicate that male children are oriented towards traditional male behaviors -such as aggressiveness and competitiveness- and that orientation creates barriers against close relationships. Since female children are oriented towards expressing their feelings more comfortably and being compassionate, they are encouraged to form close relationships with their environments (Marini, 1988; cited in: Umberson, Chen, House, Hopkins & Slaten, 1996). Roles that are regarded as traditionally female also focus on expressiveness which is associated with warmth, compassion and support behaviors (Bem, 1977). Therefore females have stronger options in work based social relations (Konrad, Ritchie, Lieb & Corrigall, 2000). From a different viewpoint, the possibility of females to experience stress (work based or other types) is higher compared to male

coworkers. Also, female employees with children have higher social work loads compared to male employees with children (Lundberg & Franenhauser, 1999). Hence, coworker support may be more valuable for female coworkers compared to male coworkers because coworkers who undergo similar experiences can share their experiences, may shoulder each other's responsibilities and sympathize with each other (Ng and Sorensen, 2008). Based on research findings, it can be argued that these are the reasons for females' higher level of coworker support perceptions. Some studies also identified that females receive more support compared to males (Liebler & Sandefur, 2002; Turner and Marino, 1994; Wellman & Wortley, 1990).

On the other hand, perceptions regarding supervisor support also did not present any significant differences based on gender but males' average scores were higher than those of females. Although both males and females have similar social circles (Moore, 1990) females are more inclined to make friends based on emotions while males form formal relationships (Booth, 1972). Relationships with supervisors are mostly based on formal relations and not on close friendships. It can be argued that that's the reason of make faculty members' perceptions relate to supervisor support. Although female coworkers are engaged in working life in various positions, they generally stay in the background. Especially in higher positions, the number of females is limited compared to the number of males (Ağıl, 2011). This situation is not different in universities. Based on the information obtained from the websites of the faculties included in the study, approximately 80% of the supervisors (rector, dean and department head) are males. Male employees can spend more time with their fellows and develop different kinds of discourses; this fact may be regarded as one of the reasons for high level of supervisor support perceptions observed in male faculty members.

3.2.2. Findings related to profession al seniority variable

Table 3 presents the results of Kruskal Wallis H test in which faculty members' Life Satisfaction, Coworker Support and Supervisor Support perceptions were examined based on professional seniority variable.

Table 3: Results of Kruskal Wallis H Test in which faculty members' life satisfaction, coworker support and supervisor support perceptions were examined based on professional seniority variable

Dimensions	Professional Seniority	N	SO	sd	χ^2	p	Source of Difference
Life Satisfaction	1. 1-5 years	75	145.09				
	2. 6-10 years	41	146.23				1-3
	3. 11-15 years	70	178.83	4	9.82	.043*	3-4
	4. 16-20 years	50	140.08				4-5
	5. 21 +	81	172.89				
Coworker Support	1. 1-5 years	75	185.71				
	2. 6-10 years	41	169.09				1-3
	3. 11-15 years	70	150.94	4	11.19	.024*	1-4
	4. 16-20 years	50	152.91				1-5
	5. 21 +	81	139.89				
Supervisor Support	1. 1-5 years	75	179.16				
	2. 6-10 years	41	145.62				
	3. 11-15 years	70	171.84	4	9.14	.058	—
	4. 16-20 years	50	141.56				
	5. 21 +	81	146.78				

According to the results of analysis presented in Table 3, faculty members' life satisfaction [$\chi^2(sd=2,n=371)=9.827$ p=.043] and Coworker Support [$\chi^2(sd=2,n=371)=11.195$ p=.024] perceptions changed significantly based on professional seniority variable. On the other hand, their perceptions regarding supervisor support [$\chi^2(sd=2,n=371)=9.141$ p=.058] did not generate significant changes according to professional seniority. Mann Whitney U test was conducted to determine the source of difference in the scales which presented significant differences.

When faculty members' life satisfaction was examined in terms of professional seniority variable, significant differences was observed between individuals with "1-5" and "11-15" years, "11-15" and "16-20" years and "16-20" and "21 years and higher seniority". Life satisfaction of individuals with "11-15" years professional seniority was found to be higher than that of individuals with "1-5" years and "16-20" years professional seniority. When the individuals with "11-15" years seniority are investigated in terms of teaching career phases, it is observed that this phase is the "experimentalism/activism" phase. It is reported that high level physical and intellectual skills are acquired at this phase and this acquisition is based on energy, effort, ambition and self-confidence and these individuals are at the peak in terms of these characteristics (Sikes, Measor & Woods, 1985; cited in: Bakioğlu, 1996). Hence, it can be argued that the energy and self-confidence possessed by these individuals

increase their life satisfaction levels. On the other hand, life satisfaction of individuals with “21 years and higher” professional seniority was found to be higher than the life satisfaction of individuals with “16-20” years professional seniority. When we regard the fact that individuals with 21 years and higher” professional seniority either have the professorship title or very close to receiving their title, it can be claimed that they are at the peak of their profession. They are at a place where they want to be and experience the relaxation generation by this achievement. They can easily publish based on accumulated knowledge. They are known in personal and professional sense and they also receive higher salaries than the other faculty members with various other titles. Hence, it can be claimed that satisfaction in their work lives significantly affect their life satisfaction. Similarly, Eren (2008) also found that professional seniority increases life satisfaction. As opposed to the findings of this study, some studies report no significant differences in life satisfaction based on professional seniority (Avşaroğlu et. al., 2005; Aysan & Bozkurt, 2004; Yılmaz & Altınok, 2009). This result may be related to the fact that these types of studies are mostly conducted on teachers. Since teachers do not follow career advancement steps like the faculty members, their professional seniority may not have massive impact on their life satisfaction levels.

According to analyses on faculty members’ coworker support perceptions, significant differences were observed between the faculty members with “1-5” years and “11-15” and “16-20” and “21 years and higher” professional seniority. Coworker support perceptions of the faculty members with “1-5” years professional seniority was found to be higher than the coworker support perceptions of the faculty members with “11-15” years, “16-20” years and “21 years and higher” professional seniority. Considering the fact that faculty members with “1-5” years professional seniority are individuals who has just entered the academic world, it can be claimed that there is no competitive environment among them yet and close relationships are flourishing. Therefore, they may have more communication with their coworkers and may share more. They are more open to help one another; they may not object to sharing information and knowledge and may be pushing personal interests into the background. Sias (2008) report that close friends at the work place have the necessary power and influence that help their achievement and career advancements. Hence, it can be argued that coworker support among the faculty members may be high. Increased in seniority and titles generate competitive environments. Different types of relationships may emerge among individuals who desire to hold positions such as head, director or rector or who are waiting for tenure.

Although there were no significant differences in faculty members’ supervisor support perceptions based on professional seniority, faculty members with “1-5” years

professional seniority were found to have the highest level perceptions in that regard. This finding is consistent with the findings obtained in the study conducted by Ceylan, Mat-Çelik and Emhan (2015). Also, another study conducted at schools provided the same result individuals who have just started their profession and who are at the initial stages of the process need information and support in many areas such as operations in the institution and universities, academic world, procedures and principles, academic advancement, conducting studies and personal rights and the persons who may provide the best support in these domains are the supervisors. Supervisors may provide both material and moral support to employees. A study conducted on research assistants who are at the first steps of their careers show that they expect material and moral support from the university management and faculty members in the department in terms of self-development (Özen & Nartgün, 2011).

3.2.3. Findings related to marital status variable

Table 4 presents the results of Mann Whitney U test which examined faculty members' Life Satisfaction, Coworker Support and Supervisor Support perceptions based on marital status variable.

Table 4: Results of Mann Whitney U test which examined faculty members' Life Satisfaction, Coworker Support and Supervisor Support perceptions based on marital status variable

	Marital Status	N	SO	ST	U	P
Life Satisfaction	Married	218	167.11	36430.50	9022.50	.01*
	Single	99	141.14	13972.50		
Coworker Support	Married	218	156.22	34056.00	10185.00	.42
	Single	99	165.12	16347.00		
Supervisor Support	Married	218	158.08	34461.50	10590.50	.79
	Single	99	161.03	15941.50		

According to the results of analyses presented in Table 4, there were significant differences in faculty members' life satisfaction perceptions ($U= 9022.500$, $p=.019$) based on marital status. It was observed that mean scores of married faculty members were higher than those of single faculty members. Examination of faculty members' coworker support ($U= 10185.000$, $p=.422$) and supervisor support ($U=10590.500$, $p=.791$) perceptions presented no significant differences based on marital status.

In terms of life satisfaction, life satisfaction experienced by married faculty members were found to be higher compared to life satisfaction experienced by single faculty members, this finding can be explained by the social support received by

married faculty members. Work and family are important in one's life and therefore are important factors that determine happiness. As pointed in Maslow's hierarchy of needs, humans need to satisfy the need for love in addition to the basic needs in order to have satisfaction. Hence, high life satisfaction level of married individuals is an expected result. The fact that extremely happy persons are not alone but have strong romantic and social relationships can explain the direct relationship between the state of being married and happiness (Diener & Seligman, 2002). Some studies also show that life satisfaction of married individuals is higher than that of the individuals who were previously married or never married (Caner, 2015; Eren, 2008; Haller & Hadler, 2006; Hayo & Seifert, 2003; Gove, Hughes & Style, 1983; Myers, 2000; Öztürk, 2014; Selim, 2008). It was found in Dikmen's (1995) study that increases in the marriage period resulted in increases in life satisfaction as well as job satisfaction. In a study conducted in 19 countries, Masteekasa (1994) found that in each country, married individuals are happier than unmarried individuals. As opposed to these findings, Stull and Scarisbrick-Hauser (1989) identified that individuals with no marriage experience had higher life satisfactions compared to married, divorced or widowed individuals. On the other hand, in their research, Aysan and Bozkurt (2004) found no significant differences in life satisfaction based on marital status but pointed to the fact that married individuals have higher life satisfaction.

No significant differences were found based on marital status in terms of coworker support and supervisor support perceptions but it was observed that support perceptions of single individuals were higher. This finding may be related to the fact that single individuals spend more time with their friends and have closer communication with them. When sharing with the social environment increases, mutual support may also increase. Therefore, this finding may be the result of more time spent with colleagues due to being single. When spousal support is considered, support received from significant others are observed not to generate meaningful differences in life satisfaction (Ruehlman & Wolchik, 1988). Hence, mutual support received from spouses can also be provided to single individuals by their friends. Previous studies report that single individuals have more communication with their friends (Rubinstein 1981; Stull & Scarisbrick-Hauser 1989; Ward 1979).

3.3. Findings and interpretation related to the third sub problem

Table 5 presents faculty members' life satisfaction and supervisor support and coworker support perceptions.

Table 5: The relationship between faculty members' life satisfaction and supervisor support and coworker support perceptions

Dimension		Life Satisfaction	Coworker Support	Supervisor Support
Life Satisfaction	r	1		
	p	0		
	N	317		
Coworker Support	r	0.253**	1	
	p	0	0	
	N	317	317	
Supervisor Support	r	0.330**	0.530**	1
	p	0	0	0
	N	317	317	317

**p<.01

Table 5 shows that, based on Spearman Rho coefficient, there was a low level, positive and statistically meaningful relationship between faculty members' coworker support perceptions and their life satisfaction perceptions ($r = .253$ $p < .01$). When their coworker support perceptions increased, their life satisfactions increased at a low level and when their coworker support perceptions decreased, their life satisfactions also decreased at a low level.

A positive, medium level and statistically significant relationship was identified between faculty members' supervisor support perceptions and their life satisfaction perceptions ($r = .330$ $p < .01$). When their supervisor support perceptions increased, their life satisfactions increased at a medium level and when their supervisor support perceptions decreased, their life satisfactions also decreased at a medium level.

The starting point of the study- possible relationship between coworker and supervisor support and life satisfaction- was validated with these results. The results showed that the relationships between faculty members' coworker support perceptions and their life satisfactions were at low levels whereas the relationships between faculty members' supervisor support perceptions and their life satisfactions were at medium levels.

Being an academician is a socially influential profession which is accepted in wide circles and which requires a professional training process (Zeynel, 2014). The individuals who have preferred this profession first of all advance in their careers and equip themselves with the necessary knowledge and skills and transfer these accumulated information to university students. Motivations, job satisfactions and life satisfactions of faculty members who are regarded as intellectual workers with intensive work conditions which necessitate constant research, learning and teaching along with self-development are crucial for effective performance. Faculty members

with high life satisfaction levels are expected to perform their duties fondly and have higher achievement. Therefore, it can be argued that a relaxed work environment in which they feel well, a supervisor who supports them and coworkers with whom they will enjoy working will be effective in increasing both their job satisfaction and their life satisfaction. Although supervisor support and coworker support –equally important as organizational support in identifying with the organization- have positive effects on individuals' life satisfaction, they are different in some aspects.

As mentioned in the literature (Ng & Sorensen, 2008), support provided by the supervisor in the organization is different from the support provided by coworkers in some aspects. Supervisors provide informational, material and emotional support to employees. Supervisor support is expected to supply more precise outputs compared to coworker support. Therefore, effects of supervisor support can be more influential on individuals' work life.

While lack of coworker support does not generate much change in achievement in the academic world which mostly focuses on individual achievements, it may affect life satisfaction in emotional aspects. Individuals spend most of their daily life at the work place and negative relationships with coworkers may negatively affect their happiness at the workplace. However, lack of supervisor support will bring other problems with it such as feeling alone in the organization, inability to get tenure, problems with administrative tasks, disregard for his/her views, lack of material support and lack of encouragement for his/her studies and therefore affect the individual in emotional as well as material terms.

Even though it was observed that supervisor support has a more direct relationship with life satisfaction, it was identified that both types of support are effective on faculty members' life satisfaction. It can be argued that life satisfaction of faculty members who receive support both from supervisors and coworkers will increase and they will be able to generate efficiency in many domains by contributing to their careers, students, universities, cities and the society with their studies and research.

5. Result and suggestions

Findings show that faculty members “partially agreed” to the questions regarding life satisfaction; “agreed” regarding Coworker Support and were “undecided” regarding Supervisor Support. It was also found that no significant differences existed in faculty members' life satisfaction, coworker support and supervisor support perceptions in terms of gender. Significant differences were observed in faculty members' life

satisfaction perceptions based on professional seniority. Life satisfaction perceptions of faculty members with "11-15" years professional seniority were found to be higher than those of faculty members "1-5" years and "16-20" years professional seniority. Also, life satisfaction perceptions of faculty members with "21 years and higher" professional seniority were found to be higher than the life satisfaction perceptions of faculty members with "16-20" years of professional seniority. Significant differences were observed in coworker support perceptions based on faculty members' professional seniority. Perceptions of faculty members with "1-5" years professional seniority were found to be higher than the perceptions of faculty members with "11-15" years, "16-20" years and "21 years and higher" professional seniority.

Significant differences were observed in faculty members' life satisfaction perceptions based on marital status. It was found that life satisfaction perceptions of married faculty members were higher compared to the life satisfaction perceptions of single faculty members. No significant differences were found in faculty members' coworker support and supervisor support perceptions based on marital status. Married and single faculty members have similar perceptions related to coworker support and supervisor support.

A positive, low level and statistically significant relationship was identified between faculty members' life satisfaction and their coworker support perceptions. A positive, medium level and statistically significant relationship was identified between their supervisor support perceptions and their life satisfaction levels. In this context, life satisfaction increased when coworker support and supervisor support increased and life satisfaction decreased when coworker support and supervisor support decreased. Suggestions below were developed in line with the findings.

- Positive work environments should be created at universities, unit supervisors should solve problems in a fair manner.
- An environment of peace should be created in units to positively affect individuals' satisfaction.
- Necessary arrangements should be undertaken in universities to provide work conditions in which faculty members will be comfortable, conduct their studies and feel happy.
- Units in faculties should make communication channels between units open. Activities that will serve to strengthen communication among faculty members working in different units should be organized.
- Group meetings should be organized by faculty members and they should produce solutions and suggestions together.

- Activities should be organized to let faculty members spend time together socially and bond.
- Unit supervisors should be sensitive to the needs of faculty members so that they can have higher life satisfaction and be more productive.
- Supervisors should adopt democratic and supportive attitudes to increase faculty members' life satisfaction.
- Senior management at universities should academically support faculty members, increase its encouragement and provide the necessary equipotent ant tools for their research and studies.
- Senior management should appreciate faculty members' achievement and make them feel valuable for the organization.

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